

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

GENGHIS KHAN'S ECONOMIC POLICY AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract

The establishment of the Mongol Empire, which spanned Eurasia, was initiated by Genghis Khan and have been successfully expanded by his successor, Ögedei Khan, and their descendants for a few hundred years. The success of this empire has been undoubtedly attributed to its military might and organization. However, in this paper, we discuss the economic policies of Genghis Khan and Ögedei Khan that potentiated the Mongol Empire's military power and helped establish a vast empire where fair trade, communication, and exchange were possible throughout Eurasia. We believe that these policies enabled the Mongol Empire's economy to be what we would call a globalized economy today.

Keywords: Economic policy, Mongol Empire, Genghis Khan, Ögedei Khan, trade policy, economic infrastructure, tax system.

The fact that Genghis Khan was a brilliant economic policymaker is confirmed by the assessment by various researchers and "Washington Post" has named him "Man of the Millennium" in the 1990s. According to Washington Post, "Genghis Khan and his successors created a vast free trade zone covering Europe and Asia, strengthening the ties between Western and Eastern civilizations. It can be said that this was the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) system of the Middle Ages. They were the first to create a communication network connecting the world 700 years before the creation of the Internet."^{1,2}

The question of what exactly the economic policy of Genghis Khan, man of the second millennium, was aimed at and by what mechanisms it was implemented, rightly attracts the attention of today's scholars. Genghis Khan's economic policy and the mechanisms by which it was implemented are recorded to some extent in historical sources such as "Mongolian Secret History", "Sudriin Chuulgan (Jāmi' al-Tawārikh)", "Mongol National Encyclopedia", "Zasakh Bilig", and "Ikh Zazag Khuuli (The Yassa)". According to these sources, in addition to implementing specific economic and business measures, Genghis Khan implemented his economic policy using taxes, customs, and rewards. The main goal of his economic policy was to eliminate any pretexts that threatened the independence and sovereignty of Mongolia, strengthen its independence in all respects, and to revive the state's economy in a short time, and to reliably ensure the economic independence and freedom of his nation.^{3,4}

In order to ensure the economic independence of the Great Mongolian Empire, he took specific measures to structurally reform the economy, such as developing

animal husbandry, regulating land relations, protecting the environment, regulating internal and external trade, economic infrastructure, state finance and the tax system, and widely use knowledge, talent, and technical and technological advances in economic activities.⁵ Thus, when implementing decisive measures to develop the economy, first of all, nomadic animal husbandry was brought under the jurisdiction of the mingghan (a social-military unit of 1000 households) and the number of livestock was intensively increased.⁶ The traditional Mongolian system of nomadic, agricultural, and military systems was changed and organized into a compact urban system. During the reign of Genghis Khan and his successors, livestock was kept under state protection and control, and was counted and accounted for annually.⁷

Within the framework of his policy on the development of livestock, he prioritized a fiscally frugal approach. Firstly, he promoted the economical use of livestock for food and economic purposes and encouraged the preservation and processing of livestock without loss. Secondly, he established proper rules for hunting various types of animals, determining under what conditions and when hunts are allowed.⁸

It is noted in the "Mongolian Secret History" that the Great Khan paid great attention to caring for his livestock, and this can be seen as an expression of his policy on agriculture. In 1206, when the Great Mongol Empire was established and Emperor Genghis Khan took over the reign, a new era began in which land relations were made a key component of state policy. In addition issues surrounding national independence, social and economic development, people's livelihood, customs, and environmental protection were legally guaranteed in a complex system.

¹ Joel Achenbach. "The era of his ways; In which we choose the most important man of the last thousand years", Washington Post, December 30, 1995.

² M. Hoang "Genghis Khan - An Emperor of All Men". New York, 2000.

³ Ishjants I. "Compilation of Mongol Historical Writings", Ulaanbaatar, 1998.

⁴ Nyamosor N. "Mongol Economy and Society in the 13th Century: Execution of Great Yasa Law", Ulaanbaatar, 1999.

⁵ Dorj Tudev, "The charm of leadership of Genghis Khan", pp 169, Ulaanbaatar, 2016.

⁶ B.Y. Vladimirtsov "Chingiz Khan; The Social system of the Mongols: Mongolian Nomadic Feudalism", Moscow, 1934.

⁷ Bayanjargal Ch. "Economic Policy and Legacy of Genghis Khan", Ulaanbaatar, 2004.

⁸ Jack Weatherford, "Genghis Khan and the Making of the Modern World", pp 84, *Crown and Three Rivers Press*, 2004.

At that time, the owner of the entire land was the ruler of the state, Genghis Khan. For other purposes, land was only lent for usage. At that time, land was divided the following 3 types;

1. The State Land. Land which is under the complete control of the Khan or the land belonging to the mingghan

2. The Protected Land. This was the land granted by Genghis Khan to the Golden family (Genghis Khan's direct relatives) for generations to own, and was called "inj".

3. The Gift Land. This was land that was awarded as a reward to nobles, military commanders, and others who had served the emperor (the state and the people) and had rendered meritorious service, and was called "tushee". Not only the lands protected by Genghis Khan, but also the lands under the authority of the Golden family, the Tumen (a social-military unit of 10000 households), and the Mingghan commanders were not their own property, but were deemed their possessions.⁹

Genghis Khan paid special attention to trading with neighboring countries, and as a result foreign merchants came to Mongolia freely. For example, the "Mongolian Secret History" records that "Genghis Khan met a merchant named Hasan of Sartuul at Lake Balzhun, who was buying ten thousand sables from Alahushdigithur of Ongud and sables and squirrels from the people living on the Ergune River."¹⁰ It is also recorded that Genghis Khan sent multiple envoys to Khorezm with a proposal to trade, but the envoys were repeatedly massacred, causing him to declare war with the country, which he the won and occupied Khorezm. Thus, with the establishment of an empire spanning Asia and Europe, a global free trade zone was established. By paying close attention to the importance of international trade relations in the development of the national economy, and by actively developing it and taking practical steps, Genghis Khan can be considered to have laid the foundation for the current economic globalization of mankind.¹¹

Among the five major Mongolian livestock, horses were of particular importance. This is because horses were not only ordinary livestock, but also were military defense and had strategic importance. In volume I of his work "Khalkh Towchoon", the famous Mongolian historian Gongor. D argues that the Ministry of Horse Breeding used to carefully count the state's horse herd every year and report to the Khan of how it grew or perished, and that no one except the Khan was allowed known the exact number of horses in the herds.¹²

Crafting also played a significant role in the Mongol economy. Since ancient times, every Mongolian had a tradition of making various weapons and ornaments from wood, clay, bone, leather, bronze, iron, gold, silver, and stone.¹³

When leading the state of the Great Mongol Empire, Emperor Genghis Khan used to reward those who had worked hard and devotedly, to stimulate their enthusiasm, activity, and interest. Genghis Khan, after seeing the results of people's work, generously rewarded those who had achieved success with high positions and valuables, regardless of their social status, whenever possible. The rewards were both material and emotional.¹⁴

In continuation of his father's policy, Ögedei Khan, while expanding Genghis Khan's political reforms, paid great attention to the issue of economic management. There is reason to believe that the success of Ögedei Khan's economic policy was associated with some of the specific advantages of his policies. During Ögedei Khan's reign, handicrafts and manufacturing were greatly encouraged. In addition to manufacturing military products such as weapons, armors, curved swords and bows suitable for slashing and shooting from horseback, great attention was paid to establishing and operating industries for the household needs of herders, such as per carts and simple carts that could be pulled by three, four, or more oxen. There is evidence that there was a smelting furnace (factory) in the city of Kharkhorum.¹⁵ Ögedei Khan established many handicraft factories in Mongolia and employed about 200 thousand domestic and foreign craftsmen and builders for crafting.¹⁶

Ögedei Khan's customs and tribute policy had a significant impact on the development of the country's economy. In 1229, he issued a law on the unified state tribute to be collected into the Khan's treasury, and established the amount and procedure for the tribute to be collected from livestock and agriculture.¹⁷ In addition, he inspected and weighed the land of foreigners who settled in Mongolia and imposed taxes. In 1233, an amendment was made to the state tax law, and a tax was levied on horses, cattle, and sheep for every 100 heads. Taxes on traders were also tightened. In 1230, the Salt Tax Law, in 1234 the Trade Customs Law, and in 1236 the Millenary Law (10.149) were issued, and customs duties were collected in accordance with world standards, taking into account the income of foreign and domestic merchants.¹⁸

An orphan support fund was established, and measures were taken to provide scholarships to the families of heroes who had died in the war, and to reduce and exempt the lower classes from taxes. In 1236, Ögedei Khan issued a decree that issued paper money, which was the first in the world. The Ministry of Internal Affairs was established in 1231 and headed by Yulai Chu Cai, the Khan's son-in-law. Yulai Chu Cai also initiated the separation of military and civil administration in the same year. This meant that the military governors and millenary governors were only responsible for military affairs, and the collection of tribute and other land affairs were handled by specially appointed officials. This was the

⁹ History of Mongol State. Vol. 5. pp 143, Ulaanbaatar, 2003.

¹⁰ The Secret History of the Mongols, Ulaanbaatar, 1990.

¹¹ Adam Hart-Davis, "History: The Definitive Visual Guide: from the Dawn of Civilization to the Present Day", London, 2007

¹² Gongor D. "Chronicle of the Khalkha Mongols. Vol. I", Ulaanbaatar, 1978.

¹³ Amar A. "A Concise History of Mongolia", Ulaanbaatar, 1989.

¹⁴ Natsagdorj Sh. "Chronicles of Genghis Khan", Ulaanbaatar, 1991.

¹⁵ Ishtseren. L, Sasada. T, et. al., "Some results of the chronological study of ancient iron ore smelting furnaces", *Ancient studies; Studies on Nomadic Cultures*, Ulaanbaatar, 2024

¹⁶ John Larner, "Marco Polo and the Discovery of the World", *Yale University Press*, 1999.

¹⁷ History of Mongol State. Vol. 5., Ulaanbaatar, 2003.

¹⁸ Unen Setsen "Studies on the Secret History of the Mongols", *Indiana University Press*, 1965.

beginning of a completely new relationship of management, separating military and civil affairs.

During the reign of Ögedei Khan, a unified monetary and financial policy was implemented throughout the Empire. A census was taken in 1233-1236. Tax and credit policies were reformed. Merchants were banned from lending money at excessively high interest rates. Ögedei Khan enriched the political and state reforms of Genghis Khan with economic reforms and business reforms. It is said that the great task of dismounting from concurring and governing the great empire built by Genghis Khan on horseback began precisely with Ögedei Khan.^{19,20}

Let us consider the purpose of the mechanisms noted in historical sources, regarding the specific economic measures, as well as the mechanisms of customs, taxes, and incentives that were used as incentives for the implementation of economic policies. Regarding taxes and customs, Genghis Khan established and implemented the norms of taxes and tributes to form the treasury of the Great Mongol Empire. The amount of official taxes varied in the regions of the Great Mongol Empire, and in general, once a year, if one head of livestock out of a hundred was less than one hundred, the official tribute was exempted, 1 tar was taxed on each hectare of grain from the peasants, and any other goods could be taxed, and the rich were obliged to pay 7-10 dinars in taxes per year.²¹ It is noted in historical records as follows, "The king, who has inherited the wealth from his great father should not burden the citizens, and should only be given a sheep from his country for soup every year. Only one sheep out of a hundred should be slaughtered, and spare some for the poor. Wonder how drink would be taken if all was taken from the citizens every time his brothers and sisters, and the great benefactors gather? He should be given a mare from each myanggan, and permanent milkers should be employed for milking, and herdsmen for herding those mares, and they should be exchanged regularly, and some should be employed for herding the foals."²²

The government of the Great Mongol Empire exempted the elderly and the disabled from taxes, and provided tax relief under certain conditions. Intellectual workers, monks, and religious figures were exempted from paying taxes within the scope of the Great Mongol Empire, and other citizens were obliged to pay customs duties. In the classical formulation of economic theory, serfs paid both product and labor for their taxes. However, the form of monetary taxes was almost nonexistent at that time.

An official called "darguchi"²³ was appointed and employed, who was responsible for conducting a census of the country's population, determining and collecting the appropriate taxes from them, and transporting them to the capital of the empire. Darguchi were special administrative representatives or deputy governors appointed by the Great Khan in the conquered territories and were the tax collectors. Initially, Darguchi were associated with military affairs, but later they became

exclusively civil servants. During the empire, the Darguchi system spread rapidly throughout the conquered countries of Asia and Europe. An example from historical reports about darguchi system is as follows, "Genghis Khan has issued a decree that "A darguchi was appointed in all settlements. Father and son named Yalav and Mashud Khurumi from the Sartuul clan, came from the Urungechi settlement and discussed the customs of their settlements with Genghis Khan, and they were told about the taxes and customs. Mashud Khurumi was appointed the chief for the settlements of Bukhara, Semisgei, Urungechi, Odan, Kisgar, Uriyan, Gusen, and Daril, while Yalav, the father, was appointed to the Khitan Enund settlement. Since they knew of the customs and traditions of settlements among the Sartan people, they were appointed to govern over the Khyatan citizens and serve as their leaders". Thus, an independent special organization with tax collectors called "Darguchi" worked throughout the empire and established tax and tribute standards, which on the one hand formed the state budget, and on the other hand, implemented flexible tax policies such as discounts and exemptions, which varied depending on the living standards of the people.

As Genghis Khan deeply felt that the independence of Mongolia would ultimately be secured by the growth of its economic power, he consistently pursued his economic policy and skillfully implemented economic levers and mechanisms, thereby developing and strengthening the economic base of all Mongolia, uniting many countries and states and established a unified Great Mongol Empire.

References

1. Joel Achenbach. "The era of his ways; In which we choose the most important man of the last thousand years", Washington Post, December 30, 1995.
2. M. Hoang "Genghis Khan - An Emperor of All Men". New York, 2000.
3. Ishjamts I. "Compilation of Mongol Historical Writings", Ulaanbaatar, 1998.
4. Nyamosor N. "Mongol Economy and Society in the 13th Century: Execution of Great Yasa Law", Ulaanbaatar, 1999.
5. Dorj Tudev, "The charm of leadership of Genghis Khan", pp 169, Ulaanbaatar, 2016.
6. B.Y. Vladimirtsov " Chingiz Khan; The Social system of the Mongols: Mongolian Nomadic Feudalism", Moscow, 1934.
7. Bayanjargal Ch. "Economic Policy and Legacy of Genghis Khan", Ulaanbaatar, 2004.
8. Jack Weatherford, "Genghis Khan and the Making of the Modern World", pp 84, Crown and Three Rivers Press, 2004.
9. History of Mongol State. Vol. 5. pp 143, Ulaanbaatar, 2003.
10. The Secret History of the Mongols, Ulaanbaatar, 1990.

¹⁹ Natsagdorj Sh. Duke Toh and his Disciples. - Ulaanbaatar, 1968.

²⁰ J. A. Boyle, "The Mongol World Empire (1206-1370)", London, 1977.

²¹ Boldbaatar. J, Baasanjav. Z, "History of the World", pp 149, Ulaanbaatar, 2002.

²² Dalai Ch. "Compilation of Some Chronicles of the Mongol's History", Ulaanbaatar, 1995.

²³ Bira. Sh, Tserensodnom. D, "Selected source of the Secret History of the Mongols", pp 255, Ulaanbaatar, 2011.

11. Adam Hart-Davis, "History: The Definitive Visual Guide: from the Dawn of Civilization to the Present Day", London, 2007
12. Gongor D. "Chronicle of the Khalkha Mongols. Vol. I", Ulaanbaatar, 1978.
13. Amar A. "A Concise History of Mongolia", Ulaanbaatar, 1989.
14. Natsagdorj Sh. "Chronicles of Genghis Khan", Ulaanbaatar, 1991.
15. Ishtseren. L, Sasada. T, et. al., "Some results of the chronological study of ancient iron ore smelting furnaces", Ancient studies; Studies on Nomadic Cultures, Ulaanbaatar, 2024
16. John Larner, "Marco Polo and the Discovery of the World", Yale University Press, 1999.
17. History of Mongol State. Vol. 5., Ulaanbaatar, 2003.
18. Unen Setsen "Studies on the Secret History of the Mongols", Indiana University Press, 1965.
19. Natsagdorj Sh. Duke Toh and his Disciples. - Ulaanbaatar, 1968.
20. J. A. Boyle, "The Mongol World Empire (1206-1370)", London, 1977.
21. Boldbaatar. J, Baasanjav. Z, "History of the World", pp 149, Ulaanbaatar, 2002.
22. Dalai Ch. "Compilation of Some Chronicles of the Mongol's History", Ulaanbaatar, 1995.
23. Bira. Sh, Tserensodnom. D, "Selected source of the Secret History of the Mongols", pp 255, Ulaanbaatar, 2011.